

Stabilities and Thermodynamics of Beryllium(II), Oxovanadium(II) and Zirconium(IV) Complexes of (L)-2-Aminobutanedioic acid-4-amide

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The stability constants of Be^{2+} , VO^{2+} and Zr^{4+} complexes of (L)-2-aminobutanedioic acid-4-amide have been determined in aqueous medium at different temperatures, viz. 25, 35 and 45° and varying ionic strengths $\mu = 0.1, 0.2, 0.5$ and $1.0 M \text{KNO}_3$ employing Calvin Melchior's extension of Bjerrum's method and refined by least-square treatment. The thermodynamic functions ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° accompanying complex formation have also been evaluated at 35°.

IN continuation of the earlier work by Sexena and coworkers¹⁻⁵ on the electrochemical behaviour of amino acids and their metal complexes, this communication reports the formation, composition and stability constants of Be^{2+} , VO^{2+} and Zr^{4+} complexes with (L)-2-aminobutanedioic acid-4-amide at different temperatures, viz. 25, 35 and 45° and ionic strengths $\mu = 0.1, 0.2, 0.5$ and $1.0 M \text{KNO}_3$ by pH-metric titration technique.

Experimental

(L)-2-Aminobutanedioic acid-4-amide (H_2A) (B D.H., England) and $\text{BeSO}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{VOSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{ZrSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and NaOH were of AnalaR grade. Their solutions were prepared in double-distilled water whose strengths were checked by standard methods⁶.

Procedure: pH measurements were made on EC digital pH meter (accuracy ± 0.01) with combined glass-calomel electrode. The temperature of the cell was maintained by a thermostat. Requisite amounts of KNO_3 were added to the solution mixture for maintaining ionic strengths. The initial pH of the solutions of Be^{2+} , VO^{2+} , Zr^{4+} salts and the ligand were measured and found to be in the vicinity of 3.80, 3.19, 2.50 and 5.96, respectively. At these acidic pH values, the metal salt solution did not indicate any hydrolysis. The experimental procedure as described earlier¹ involves a series of pH titrations of the ligand with standard NaOH solution in the absence and presence of metal ions at different metal-ligand ratios.

For qualitative detection of complex formation, stoichiometric pH titrations were performed for

the following solutions containing the metal and ligand in different molar ratios of 1:1, 1:2 and 1:4 against $0.1 M \text{NaOH}$ (total vol. 25 ml): (i) $4 \times 10^{-3} M \text{H}_2\text{A}$, (ii) $4 \times 10^{-3} M \text{H}_2\text{A} + 4 \times 10^{-3} M \text{M}^{n+}$, (iii) $4 \times 10^{-3} M \text{H}_2\text{A} + 2 \times 10^{-3} M \text{M}^{n+}$ and (iv) $4 \times 10^{-3} M \text{H}_2\text{A} + 1 \times 10^{-3} M \text{M}^{n+}$

After each addition of the titrant NaOH , pH meter readings were noted. Curves were plotted between pH and moles of alkali required per mole of ligand 'm', and from the inflections in the curves, metal-ligand combining ratio was obtained. The stability constants of metal-ligand complexes were evaluated by employing Calvin and Melchior's extension⁷ of Bjerrum's⁸ pH titration technique keeping the ratio of metal to ligand constant at 1:5, using $4 \times 10^{-3} M \text{HClO}_4$ for initial lowering of the buffer region and preventing hydrolysis.

Formation function $\bar{n}$ and free ligand concentration $[A]$ were calculated by using the standard expression from the titration curves drawn. The pK_1 and pK_2 values of the dissociation of the ligand at different temperatures and ionic strengths have already been reported by the authors⁹ and used in the calculations.

Results and Discussion

The formation curves were obtained by plotting $\bar{n}$ vs $-\log A$. The stability constants are determined by noting $-\log A$ values at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and 1.5, which indicated the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 metal-ligand complexes. It was observed that Be^{2+} , VO^{2+} and Zr^{4+} complexes with the ligand were formed in the pH ranges 3.8-7.2, 3.3-6.5 and 2.2 to 4.0, respec-

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS OF Be^{2+} , VO^{2+} AND Zr^{4+} COMPLEXES WITH (L)-2-AMINOBTANEDIOIC ACID-4-AMIDE

Metal	Temp. 25° μ 0.1	35°					45°	
		0.0	0.1	0.2	0.5	1.0	0.1	
Be^{2+}	log K_1	6.25	6.55	6.60	6.65	6.85	7.10	6.85
	log K_2	4.95	5.25	5.30	5.35	5.55	5.80	5.65
	log β	11.20	11.80	11.90	12.00	12.40	12.90	12.50
	log β ^a	11.28		11.88	12.04	12.35	12.79	12.55
VO^{2+}			11.80					
	log K_1	7.05	7.25	7.30	7.35	7.45	7.70	7.50
	log K_2	6.45	6.55	6.60	6.85	7.00	7.20	6.80
	log β	13.50	13.80	13.90	14.20	14.45	14.90	14.30
			13.70	13.79	14.05	14.25	14.99	14.10
Zr^{4+}	log K_1	8.50	8.70	8.75	8.80	8.90	9.00	9.00
	log K_2	7.55	7.65	7.70	7.75	7.90	8.05	7.90
	log β	16.05	16.35	16.45	16.55	16.80	17.05	16.90
	log β ^a	16.09	16.36	16.48	16.36	16.84	16.96	17.00

^a Represents stability constant obtained by least-square treatment. Uncertainty limit upto ± 0.02–0.04.

tively, beyond which slight precipitation occurred. The log K_1 and log K_2 values of metal-ligand complexes were determined at temperatures 25, 35 and 45° and ionic strengths 0.1, 0.2, 0.5 and 1.0 M and further refined by least-square treatment (the difference between log K_1 and log K_2 being less than 1.78) (Table 1) which shows the following order of stabilities: $\text{Be}^{2+} < \text{VO}^{2+} < \text{Zr}^{4+}$.

Stability constants gradually increase with rise in temperature showing thereby that higher temperature favours the formation of complexes and their stability. Further, log K values are found to increase with the increase in ionic strengths (Table 1). Thermodynamic stabilities were obtained by the extrapolation of measured formation constants to zero ionic strength.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTION OF METAL-LIGAND COMPLEXES AT 35° AND ZERO IONIC STRENGTH

Metal complex	−ΔG° kcal mol ^{−1}	ΔH° kcal mol ^{−1}	ΔS° cal K ^{−1} mol ^{−1}
Be^{2+}	16.6 (±0.6)	27.7 (±0.8)	144.0 (±4.5)
VO^{2+}	19.5 (±0.8)	18.0 (±0.6)	121.6 (±4.4)
Zr^{4+}	23.0 (±0.7)	18.7 (±0.4)	135.6 (±3.8)

Thermodynamic parameters, such as free energy (ΔG°), enthalpy (ΔH°) and entropy (ΔS°) accompanying complexation are determined at 35° with the help of standard equations¹⁰ and are summarised in Table 2. The negative values of ΔG° show

that the reaction tends to proceed spontaneously. The positive values of enthalpy indicate the endothermic nature of the reaction suggesting that higher temperature favours chelation process, in fair agreement with increasing stability with temperature. The positive values of entropy also favour the chelation process.

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